

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.413 Max: 62.5343	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1472 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	 <small>UNIVERSITY OF MICHIGAN</small> <small>Rubio Museum of Archaeology</small> Gabii Project
	In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #:	
DEFINITION plateau in elongation of SU 1468			Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:		Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		
				<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
			Compaction		Color	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft		<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						
Northern Limit			<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original	
Southern Limit			<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			
Western Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			
Eastern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:			Abuts:			
Is covered by: 1327			Covers:			
Is cut by: 1390			Cuts:			
Is filled by:			Fills:			
OBSERVATIONS						
dry, sunny conditions SU is still in situ						
DESCRIPTION						
Position within sector: south central edge of Area B 204						
Shape: long rectangular						
For layers complete this section:						
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):						
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)						
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):						
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commigled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)						
For cuts complete this section:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight						
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping						
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular						
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
Observations:						

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size: Small (range) 5-10 Medium (range) 15 Large (range) 30-40 Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz
cm cm cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

lengths 106 cm, ^{width} 50 cm, height: 2 cm

Description:

stone plateau, only visible from above, SU has not been excavated

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Stone assemblage which seems to have some square regularity to it. It might be part of an earlier wall.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

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